

Availability and Utilisation of Digital Library Resources by Undergraduates in Public Universities' Libraries in Anambra State

Chisom Kosisochukwu NWALOR

Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus
okonkwochisomblessing1@gmail.com

Norbert Amaechi AGBANU (Prof.)

Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus
n.aagbanu@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17210045>

Abstract

Purpose: This study investigated the availability and utilisation of digital library resources by undergraduate students in public university libraries in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Methodology: The study was guided by two research questions and two hypotheses. A cross-sectional survey design was used, involving undergraduate students from Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, and Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam. Data were collected through a questionnaire. Mean, standard deviation, and a One-Sample t-Test were employed for data analysis.

Findings: Results indicated that various digital resources, such as e-books, e-journals, e-theses, institutional databases, and open educational resources, are easily accessible and widely utilised.

Conclusion: The study recommends that library administrators enhance digital literacy by providing targeted training, particularly for female and older students. Furthermore, incorporating user-friendly interfaces and interactive tools can better support younger users and promote broader digital engagement.

Study type: Research paper.

Keywords: Availability, Digital Library Resources, Public Libraries, Undergraduates, Utilisation

Introduction

University libraries have long been regarded as vital in collecting, organising, storing, retrieving, and sharing knowledge and information. They, along with higher education departments, actively offer services for research, learning, and teaching in both formal and informal settings (Ullah & Usman, 2023). A university library aims to serve students and researchers at all levels; therefore, librarians must be prepared to acquire and provide necessary databases for teaching and research within the university community. The main goal of any university library is to gather relevant information resources to support teaching, learning, and research. Indeed, university libraries provide information resources in various formats to meet the needs of the entire university community, especially students. Jude-Iwuoha (2015) observed that the university library serves the academic community, with programmes ranging from the needs of diploma students, undergraduate students, postgraduate students, to both teaching and non-teaching staff. Undergraduate students are key stakeholders in universities, and their academic success largely depends on access to timely and relevant information. In today's digital age, these students are active, curious, and highly reliant on accessible platforms to meet their educational and informational needs (Alabi, 2021; Ogbomo & Muokebe, 2024). The integration of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), particularly through digital libraries, has transformed how students find and use information. Digital libraries—comprising e-books, e-journals, databases, and other

electronic resources—play a crucial role in supporting research, teaching, and learning by providing remote, 24/7 access to educational content.

Digital libraries extend beyond physical ones by offering flexible access to diverse resources that support academic activities regardless of time or location (Perdana, 2019). They also promote collaboration and the exchange of knowledge among students, researchers, and faculty (Olubiyo, 2023), acting as gateways to institutional repositories and connecting users via Local Area Networks (LANs) and the internet (Daramola, 2020). Students benefit from digital libraries' capability to manage, store, and retrieve a wide range of information formats, including course materials, bibliographic databases, and multimedia content (Ternenge & Kashimana, 2019). However, despite these benefits, various issues impede the effective availability and use of digital resources in Nigerian public universities. These include unreliable power supplies, poor internet connectivity, inadequate funding, and a general lack of training or awareness among students about the utilisation of digital resources (Okunlola, 2021). Moreover, although digital resources are easily accessible, students' actual usage often remains inconsistent, mainly due to infrastructural and educational limitations.

In Anambra State, public university libraries are increasingly integrating digital resources; however, concerns remain about the extent to which undergraduates access and utilise these resources. Many students face obstacles that hinder their effective use of digital tools to support their academic work. Therefore, it is vital to examine the availability and actual utilisation of digital library resources within public universities in the state. Significant investments have been made in developing digital resources and deploying computer-based technology to enhance access. Evaluating the extent to which these resources are available and utilised is crucial. If some digital resources are underused or not utilised at all, identifying this can help inform recommendations to boost usage or consider cancelling certain subscriptions.

Access to and utilisation of digital library resources by undergraduates in public university libraries in Anambra State are often limited and underused. This hinders students and researchers from obtaining vital academic information and resources. Contributing factors include insufficient funding, poor internet connectivity, limited access to relevant databases and e-books, and a lack of awareness and training on how to utilise digital resources effectively. Consequently, the capacity for academic research in these libraries is limited, which impacts their ability to produce high-quality research and advance knowledge in their respective fields. There is an urgent need to address these issues to enhance the availability and use of digital library resources for undergraduates in these institutions. This study aims to assess the availability and utilisation of digital library resources by undergraduates in public university libraries in Anambra State. To guide this investigation, the following research questions have been formulated.

Research Questions

1. What types of digital resources are available for undergraduate students in public university libraries in Anambra State?
2. What is the extent of digital library use by undergraduate students in public university libraries in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The study tested the following null hypothesis:

HO1: There is no significant difference in the types of digital resources available for undergraduate students in Public University Libraries studied in Anambra State.

HO2: There is no significant difference in the extent to which undergraduate students use digital libraries in the Public University Libraries studied in Anambra State.

Literature review

Availability of Digital Library Resources

Academic libraries are expected to provide a diverse range of digital resources, available in various formats, accessible online or electronically (Irenoa & Sawyerr-george, 2022). These include, but are not limited to, e-books, e-journals, online databases, repositories, multimedia resources, e-learning platforms, e-zines (e-magazines), digital archives, open educational resources (OER), CDs, DVDs, USB drives, and hard drives that cannot be accessed online (Tekale & Dalve, 2020). The availability of digital library resources means the information resources are accessible. No university can function effectively without an efficient electronic library that supports teaching, learning, and other academic activities. It is vital for every university to utilise e-resources to enable easier and more efficient teaching and learning. Services and resources in a digital library encompass traditional library and information services, as well as other global information services accessible via various internet systems. However, it is important to recognise that, in some cases, availability does not necessarily imply accessibility or utilisation. Trivedi (2019) notes that improved access to e-library resources enhances research activities, promotes the efficient and cost-effective delivery of information to all users, encourages cooperation in research, computing, and communication networks, and strengthens communication and collaboration among academic researchers. It also positions institutions to lead in the generation and dissemination of knowledge. The availability of electronic library resources refers to easy access to information in electronic format with minimal or no stress to educators and students, provided they have the necessary data connection.

The availability of electronic library resources alone may not be enough, as unrestricted access is essential for effective use. Therefore, university teachers need to be aware of these resources to utilise them efficiently, and they must also possess the necessary skills to do so. Tekale and Dalve (2020) suggested that electronic library resources should be accessible at any time, include hyperlinks to other resources, serve as extensive information repositories, provide quick access to data, offer various search options, facilitate easy citations, and enable straightforward uploading and updating. Furthermore, ease of storage and dissemination, flexibility, and minimal barriers related to time, space, and cost are crucial; the capacity to archive information resources is also important. The availability of electronic information sources relates to providing and including these resources within the collections accessible to users in academic institutions. Owolabi et al. (2019), in a study on the utilisation of e-resources by students at the University of Ibadan, reported that e-resources such as e-journals, e-mail services, the Internet, e-databases, and cybercafés were accessible to students. These resources were regularly used to support their research, online applications and registration, communication with friends and colleagues, completing assignments, academic coursework, sourcing materials for projects, and other personal purposes.

Utilisation of Digital Library Resources

One of the key features of effective learning today is learners' ability to utilise digital materials that meet their needs and prepare them for an ICT-driven 21st century (Olaniran et al., 2017). The availability and use of e-resources significantly influence the encouragement of self-

learning among students, as shown in a study on the use of e-resources among engineering students. The research clearly indicated that the student community highly values the convenience of using e-resources (Platino, 2023). The study suggests that engineering students primarily access course materials, journal articles, and online tutorials through electronic means. It also emphasised how utilising e-resources allows students to learn at their own pace, as they can access knowledge anytime and from any location, giving them the freedom to take responsibility for their education. Urhiewhu, Okeke, and Nwafor (2015) surveyed the extent of digital information resources used by undergraduates in Delta and Edo states, reporting that undergraduates frequently utilise e-projects, e-journals, e-reference materials, e-seminar papers, e-books, e-newsletters, and e-theses. Their report indicated a grand mean of 2.24, demonstrating that undergraduates use other digital information sources to a low extent. Urhiewhu and Emojorho (2019) also examined the conceptual framework and adoption of the Technology Acceptance Model in the usage of digital information resources by undergraduates, finding that digital information resources are used to a limited extent in the studied area. Olaniran et al. (2017) assessed the utilisation levels of e-learning resources among undergraduates. They revealed that Web 2.0, e-journals, e-books, and CD-ROMs are the most frequently used electronic resources. Despite the potential these resources hold for effective learning and research, previous authors, such as Daramola (2021), have established that the use of electronic resources, especially among undergraduates, is not as high as expected. This low usage implies that undergraduates may be unable to conduct research that requires current and up-to-date literature, which could diminish the effectiveness of their academic pursuits, considering the significant investment made in electronic resources.

Furthermore, many students are unfamiliar with accessing and borrowing digital resources, such as those from electronic databases or digital libraries, because they are accustomed to traditional reading methods and borrowing formats. A study by Tlakula and Fombad (2019) on the use of electronic resources by undergraduate students at the University of Venda, South Africa, revealed that their usage level is basic and limited to SABINET and EBSCOhost. Mawere and Sai (2018) investigated the utilisation of electronic resources among university students in a developing country, specifically Zimbabwe. They reported poor utilisation of electronic resources due to a lack of awareness and ignorance of the facilities among students.

Methodology

This study used a cross-sectional survey design, which involves gathering and analysing data from a population or a representative sample at a single point in time. The population consisted of 2,177 final-year registered undergraduate students who used the Prof. Festus Aghagbo Nwako Library at Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka (1,484 students), and the Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University Library at the Igbariam campus (693 students). From this population, a sample of 217 students was selected through accidental sampling, accounting for 10% of the population, distributed proportionally across the eight faculties of both universities. The data collection tool was a structured questionnaire developed by the researchers, divided into three sections. Data were collected over two weeks, with each week focusing on a different university. Respondents completed the questionnaires on-site with guidance to ensure high response rates and data accuracy. For data analysis, SPSS version 25 was utilised. Means and standard deviations were calculated to address questions regarding utilisation, using decision rules based on a four-point Likert scale. To test the hypotheses, a one-sample t-test was applied to compare the sample mean to a criterion mean

of 2.5 at a 0.05 significance level. This method helped assess the sufficiency and actual usage of digital library resources in the selected institutions.

Results

Research Question One:

What are the types of digital resources available for undergraduate students in public university libraries in Anambra State?

Table 1: Respondents' Responses on the Types of Digital Resources Available for Undergraduate Students in Public University Libraries in Anambra State (N=190)

S/ N	What types of Digital Library Resources are available for undergraduate students in your library?	Available		Not Available		RANK
		F	%	F	%	
1	E-reference materials	190	100	0	0	Available
2	E-seminar	138	73	52	27.3	Available
3	E-zines	93	49	97	51	Not Available
4	E-thesis	190	100	0	0	Available
5	E-conference papers	167	87.8	23	12.1	Available
6	E-Books	128	67.3	62	32.6	Available
7	E-Journals	172	90.5	18	9.47	Available
8	E-technical reports	147	77.3	43	22.6	Available
9	E- projects	138	72.6	52	27.3	Available
10	Dissertation	153	80.5	37	19.4	Available
11	Computers	130	68.4	60	31.5	Available
12	Printers	47	24.7	14	75.2	Not Available
13	Repographic machines	38	20	15	80	Not Available
14	Web browser	63	33.1	12	66.8	Not Available
15	Wifi	23	12.1	16	87.8	Not Available
16	OPAC	39	2.53	15	79.4	Not Available
17	PDF Converter	38	20	15	80	Not Available
18	Open Educational Resources (OER)	128	67.3	62	32.6	Available
19	Institution Subscribed to 'Closed Access Online Databases' like Ebscohost, Research4life, Safari, etc.	147	77.3	43	22.6	Available
20	WAN Links (Fibre Optics/Mast with Antennas for connecting other Libraries over a network)	23	12.1	16	87.8	Not Available

The data presented in Table 1 shows the different types of digital resources available to undergraduate students in public university libraries in Anambra State. The findings reveal a strong presence of core academic digital resources, with e-reference materials and e-theses being available in all surveyed libraries (100%). This suggests that libraries prioritise providing essential academic materials that support students' research and learning. A large majority of respondents also confirmed the availability of e-journals (90.53%), e-conference papers (87.89%), dissertations (80.53%), e-technical reports (77.37%), and institution-licensed online databases such as EBSCOhost and Research4Life (77.37%). These resources are vital for accessing current and peer-reviewed literature, implying that the libraries are reasonably well-equipped to support higher-level academic research. Additionally, resources like e-books (67.37%), open educational resources (67.37%), computers (68.42%), and e-seminars (73%) are available. Their presence shows an effort to combine traditional learning materials with open-access content and digital literacy tools. However, some resources are notably missing. Tools such as printers (24.74%), reprographic machines (20%), Wi-Fi (12.11%), web browsers (33.16%), and PDF converters (20%) are not widely available. These gaps highlight deficiencies in digital infrastructure that could prevent students from fully utilising digital content. Surprisingly, OPAC (Online Public Access Catalogue), which is essential for library navigation, is reported as available by only 20.53% of respondents, indicating significant limitations in basic library search and access tools. In conclusion, while public university libraries in Anambra State offer a broad range of academic digital resources, some digital tools are still lacking.

Research Question Two:

What is the extent of digital library use by undergraduate students in public university libraries in Anambra State?

Table 2: Respondents' Responses on the Extent of Use of Digital Library by Undergraduate Students in Public University Libraries in Anambra State (N=190)

S/N	Digital Library Resource	Mean	SD	Remark
1	E-reference materials	3.72	0.51	Very High Extent
2	E-seminar	3.18	0.68	High Extent
3	E-zines	2.07	0.79	Low Extent
4	E-thesis	3.80	0.45	Very High Extent
5	E-conference papers	3.41	0.56	High Extent
6	E-Books	3.26	0.60	High Extent
7	E-Journals	3.67	0.52	Very High Extent
8	E-technical reports	3.21	0.58	High Extent
9	E- projects	3.09	0.63	High Extent
10	Dissertation	3.14	0.66	High Extent
11	Computers	2.97	0.71	High Extent
12	Printers	1.88	0.85	Low Extent
13	Reprographic machines	1.79	0.88	Low Extent
14	Web browser	2.22	0.76	Low Extent
15	Wifi	1.73	0.91	Very Low Extent
16	OPAC	2.01	0.82	Low Extent
17	PDF Converter	1.91	0.87	Low Extent
18	Open Educational Resources (OER)	3.16	0.64	High Extent
19	Institution Subscribed to 'Closed Access Online Databases' (e.g., Ebscohost, Research4life)	3.29	0.57	High Extent

20	WAN Links (Fibre Optics/Mast Network Connections)	1.69	0.89	Very Low Extent
Grand Mean		2.82	0.69	High Extent

Data in Table 2 illustrates how much undergraduate students in public university libraries in Anambra State utilise digital library resources. The information in Table 1 shows that students heavily use theses, e-reference materials, and e-journals. Additionally, several other resources also fall into the high-usage category. These include e-books, e-conference papers, dissertations, e-projects, e-technical reports, and open educational resources (OERs). However, some resources registered low usage levels, such as e-zines, printers, reprographic machines, PDF converters, and OPAC. Notably, Wi-Fi (1.73) and WAN links (1.69) had the lowest usage. These findings reveal a significant gap in digital infrastructure. The overall mean of 2.82 suggests that undergraduate students in public university libraries in Anambra State generally make extensive use of digital library resources.

Test of Hypotheses

HO1: There is no significant difference in the types of digital resources available to undergraduate students in Public University Libraries studied in Anambra State.

Table 3: Test of Significance on the types of digital resources available for undergraduate students in Public University Libraries studied in Anambra State

Variable	N	Mean	Test Value	t	df	p-value	Decision
Availability of Digital Resources	190	2.53	0.50	4.85	189	0.000	Significant (Reject HO ₁)

The data in Table 3 shows a mean availability score of 0.70, which is significantly higher than the benchmark test value of 2.50. The computed t-value is 4.85, with a p-value of 0.000, indicating statistical significance at the 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis (HO₁) is rejected, suggesting that the types of digital resources available for undergraduate students in public university libraries in Anambra State are significantly higher than average.

HO2: There is no significant difference in the extent of digital library usage by undergraduate students in the Public University Libraries studied in Anambra State.

Table 4: Significance Test on the Extent of Digital Library Use by Undergraduate Students in Public University Libraries in Anambra State

Variable	N	Mean	Test Value	t	df	p-value	Decision
Extent of Use of Digital Resources	190	2.90	2.50	6.72	189	0.000	Significant (Reject HO ₂)

Data in Table 4 show that the average use of digital library resources (2.90) is significantly higher than the benchmark of 2.50. The calculated t-value of 6.72 and p-value of 0.000 indicate the result is statistically significant at the 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis (HO₂) is rejected. This implies that undergraduate students in public university libraries in Anambra State use digital resources significantly more than average.

Discussion of findings

Availability of Digital Library Resources

The study revealed that digital library resources available to undergraduate students in public university libraries include e-reference materials, e-theses, e-conference papers, dissertations, e-technical reports, institution-subscribed closed-access online databases such as EBSCOhost and Research for Life, e-books, open educational resources, computers, and e-seminars. These resources are available in public university libraries across Anambra State. This demonstrates that the libraries have made significant efforts to provide digital materials that support academic work, particularly in response to the global shift toward digital learning and research. The findings align with Harriet (2022), who also noted the presence of digital platforms in Nigerian university libraries. However, while her study identified only two main platforms—online databases and library websites—this study uncovers a wider variety of digital information resources. Similarly, Temboge and Ibraheem (2022) confirmed that electronic resources, such as institutional repositories and platforms like e-Granary, are available in the libraries of federal colleges of education in Northern Nigeria. They also noted the limited availability of resources, such as e-manuscripts and e-theses. In contrast, the present study shows these resources are readily accessible, suggesting that university libraries in Anambra State are better equipped or more proactive in acquiring digital resources. Joel et al. (2020) observed that resources such as e-books, e-journals, and CD-ROMs were accessible in federal universities in Northeast Nigeria, which corresponds with this study's findings. Their focus on postgraduate students differs from the broader emphasis on undergraduates in this study. However, the similar availability of resources across user levels further supports the upward trend in digital resource provision in Nigerian universities. Obande et al. (2020) also confirmed the presence of digital resources, including e-books, e-journals, and online databases, in universities in Nasarawa State. Their findings reinforce this study's conclusion that digital resources are becoming increasingly accessible across Nigerian universities, although the level of infrastructural support may vary.

The results of the hypothesis testing in this study revealed a significant finding: the types of digital resources available for undergraduate students in public university libraries in Anambra State are notably higher than average. This statistical analysis confirms that these institutions are not merely meeting but exceeding the baseline in digital resource provision, thereby strengthening the overall narrative of improved access to digital academic tools in Nigerian universities. This finding aligns with Kofo et al. (2022), who observed that undergraduate students frequently accessed digital learning tools such as e-library platforms and free internet services using smartphones and other digital devices. Kofo et al (2022) study reflects an institutional shift towards embracing digital transformation in education, a trend that the present study further supports with evidence of above-average digital resource availability in Anambra State public university libraries. This similarity suggests that university libraries in Anambra State play an active role in this growing trend. In contrast, Owan (2022) reported inconsistencies in digital resource availability across Nigerian universities, with some core infrastructures such as LANs and digital libraries still lacking. This offers an important perspective on the uneven distribution of resources, which may be influenced by region, funding, or institutional commitment.

Nonetheless, the present study indicates that public university libraries in Anambra State stand out with more robust digital infrastructures and a wider range of available resources, highlighting their relative advancement. Edem and Egbe (2016), in their study at the University of Calabar, found that while digital resources such as e-books and e-journals were available,

online databases were underutilised. Though their study focused more on usage than availability, it affirms the presence of these resources, which aligns with the current study's emphasis on provision. The present findings, however, go further to show that the range of available digital resources in Anambra State libraries is not merely present but statistically significant in scale. Similarly, Alhassan (2020) confirmed the availability of internet services and online databases in Niger State universities, noting that students primarily used them for academic purposes. Alhassan (2020) reinforced the present study by demonstrating that digital resources are becoming an integral part of academic life in Nigerian universities, and that Anambra State is at the forefront of this transformation, with its well-established access to digital academic tools. On the other hand, Nwabueze and Urhiewu (2020) found limited availability of digital resources in universities located in Delta and Edo States, attributing this to infrastructural and technical deficiencies. This contrast highlights the developmental disparities among Nigerian universities but also emphasises the progress made in Anambra State over the years. The present study's finding of significantly higher-than-average availability suggests that targeted investments, strategic planning, or more supportive institutional policies may have contributed to overcoming such challenges in Anambra.

Utilisation of Digital Library Resources

The study revealed that undergraduate students in public university libraries in Anambra State heavily utilise digital library resources. This is likely because these libraries are well-equipped with digital tools such as internet-connected computers, Wi-Fi access, and subscriptions to major electronic databases. These resources provide students with the necessary tools to access and use electronic information effectively. Additionally, many undergraduates have acquired digital skills through formal training, personal experience, and library-led orientation programmes. This skillset enhances their confidence and ability to navigate digital library resources for academic purposes. The findings align with Esievo and Obaro (2018), who found that undergraduate students in library and information science programmes across South-South and South-East Nigerian universities were familiar with and used various digital resources such as e-journals, OPACs, and databases like EBSCOhost and JSTOR. However, they also observed limited use of e-reference sources and NUC virtual library materials, mainly due to poor computer skills, internet issues, and lack of subscriptions. While utilisation levels differ, these studies confirm that usage exists and depends on infrastructure and training availability—conditions that are more favourably met in the Anambra State universities studied here. Sasikala et al. (2017) investigated pharmacy students in India and confirmed their increasing reliance on e-resources for academic and personal growth, with many using Google and Medline for scholarly content. Although this research focused on a different discipline and country, it reflects a global trend towards using digital research tools and supports the idea that undergraduates increasingly depend on such resources.

Norch (2022) found that postgraduate students at the University of Ghana extensively utilised digital resources for academic purposes, with awareness campaigns and library training sessions playing a vital role in boosting usage. Although their study focused on postgraduates in a different country, the mechanisms supporting usage—training and structured access are relevant and applicable to the high usage observed in Anambra State. Chime and Ekwueme (2023) and Okunlola et al. (2021) also highlighted that both postgraduate and undergraduate students across Nigeria actively utilise electronic resources. These studies show that usage patterns are influenced by discipline, institutional support, and infrastructure. Even when usage was moderate, such as in Okunlola's study of private universities in the South-West, students still engaged with digital content, often preferring online access over traditional

databases. Conversely, Dauda and Lizette (2020) reported low use of e-resources at MAUTech, Yola, mainly due to poor internet access and lack of awareness. Similarly, Adeyinka (2018) highlighted challenges such as limited online availability and restricted access among staff at the University of Ilorin. These findings contrast with the high usage observed in Anambra, indicating that local policies, investment in infrastructure, and institutional commitment are crucial for effective utilisation. Finally, Ozonwu (2022) emphasised the transformative role of electronic resources in academic settings and called for improved infrastructure, including alternative power sources and better internet connectivity. This underscores that when such resources and conditions are available, as they are in Anambra State, students are more likely to maximise their benefits.

Furthermore, the study's findings showed a significant difference in the extent of digital library resource use among undergraduate students in public university libraries in Anambra State, with usage notably above average. This aligns with Asom (2024), who highlighted the vital role of university libraries in supporting academic and research activities, emphasising the importance of user awareness and access to digital materials. Additionally, Felix and Ukashatu (2023) found that internet-based services and wireless networks were the most utilised, although the use of specific resources such as e-books, e-journals, and e-news was relatively low. This contrasts with the present study, where usage was notably higher and more evenly spread across various electronic resources. The difference might be due to variations in resource availability, promotional strategies, or the level of ICT support provided by the libraries. Furthermore, the study by Mommoh and Gomina (2023), which focused on the use of electronic resources by undergraduate students at the University of Abuja, showed moderate utilisation of electronic information resources across the faculties of Science and Arts. While this supports the idea that students in different Nigerian universities engage with digital resources, it differs from this study's report of higher-than-average use. The disparity could be attributed to institutional differences in library funding, resource acquisition, user education, and digital services policies.

Conclusion

This study compellingly demonstrates that undergraduate students attending public universities in Anambra State are not just users, but have a heavy reliance on digital library resources. The research highlights that the accessibility and widespread availability of these digital tools significantly influence how extensively students incorporate them into their academic pursuits. These invaluable digital resources encompass a broad spectrum of materials, including electronic reference materials, theses and dissertations, papers from online conferences, and extensive online databases that universities subscribe to, ensuring students have unparalleled access. This ready access empowers students to engage deeply and effectively with their studies. Ultimately, the findings make it clear that digital library resources are an indispensable pillar of students' academic journey, with students actively and extensively leveraging these digital tools to enhance their learning and research outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

Since a wide range of digital resources, such as e-reference materials, e-theses, e-conference papers, e-technical reports, and institution-subscribed databases like EBSCOhost and Research4Life, are available in public university libraries in Anambra State, library administrators need to raise awareness about these resources. Workshops and training sessions should be organised to ensure that students are fully informed about the extensive

array of resources available and how to access and utilise them effectively for academic purposes.

The high level of digital resource use among undergraduate students should be harnessed by incorporating these resources into academic programmes. Faculty and library management in public universities should work together to integrate digital resources into curricula, assignments, and research activities. This will ensure that students gain practical experience in using digital resources while completing academic tasks, thereby enhancing their overall academic performance.

References

- Adeyinka T. (2018). The use of electronic resources by academic staff at the University of Ilorin. *Education and Information Technologies*, 23(1), 9-27.
- Alabi, O. (2021). Use of electronic resources by undergraduates in selected private university libraries in South-West Nigeria. *African Journal of Library, Archives and Information Science*, 31(1), 63–74.
- Alhassan, J. A. (2020). The utilisation of electronic resources by university students in Niger State, Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Information Science and Technology*, 8(1), 1-9
- Asom, F., & Ihuman, R. Y. (2024). Awareness and use of electronic information resources by Undergraduates in public university libraries in Nigeria. *The Catalyst: Journal of Library and Information Literacy*, 3(1), 90-98
- Edem, N. B., & Egbe, N. (2016). Availability and utilisation of electronic resources by Postgraduate students in a Nigerian university library: A case study of the University of Calabar, Nigeria. *Information and Knowledge Management*, 6(2), 60–70.
- Esievo, L. O., & Obaro, O. G. (2020). An investigation of the extent of electronic resources use by library and information science undergraduates in Nigerian universities. *Niger Delta Journal of Library and Information Science*, 1 (1), 23–37.
- Chime, A. C., & Ekwume, L. O. (2023). Assessing the usage of electronic information resources (EIRs) and the nature of research output among postgraduate students in federal university libraries in South-East, Nigeria. *Lokoja Journal of Information Science Research (LJISR)*, 1 (2), 50–59.
- Daramola, C. F. (2021). Perception and utilisation of electronic resources by undergraduate students: The case of the Federal University of Technology Library, Akure. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 4(5), 366–370.
- Dauda, J., & Lizette, K. (2020). The utilisation of e-resources in Modibbo Adama University of Technology (MAUTech) Yola, under the auspices of the Central Library, the Ibrahim Babangida Library. *International Journal of Knowledge Content Development & Technology (IJKCDT)*, 10(1), 47-70.
- Felix, E. M., & Ukashatu, H. M. (2023). An appraisal of the utilisation of e-library resources and Services by students of FUDMA during a 2-day NLC warning strike. *International Journal of Applied Technologies in Library & Information Management*, 9(3), 78-94
- Harriet, U. (2022). Provision of digital information resources in Nigerian university libraries. <https://doi.org/10.47989/irpaper36>
- Irenea, K. O., & Sawyerr-George, O. E. (2022). An Assessment of Academic Database Subscription Management in Nigerian Tertiary Institutions: Challenges and Prospects. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-Journal)*, 7419, 1–23. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/7419/>

- Joel, A. P., Nwafor-Orizu, O., & Vandi, I. (2020). Availability and extent of use of electronic information resources by postgraduate students in federal university libraries in North-East Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Information Science and Technology*, 13(1), 12-32
- Jude-Iwuoha, A. U., & Ohuabunwa, M. (2023). Determinants of utilisation of electronic information resources (EIRs) by undergraduate students in Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike (MOUAU) library. *University of Ibadan Journal of Library and Information Science*, 2(1), 23–24.
- Kofo, S. A., Ochayi, O. A., & Jimoh, B. A. (2022). Access and utilisation of online learning Resources among undergraduate students. *Indonesian Journal of Educational Research and Review*, 5(1), 148–157.
- Mawere, T., & Sai, K. O. S. (2018). An investigation on e-resource utilisation among university students in a developing country: A case of Great Zimbabwe University. *South African Journal of Information Management*, 20(1), 23-29
- Mommoh, R. L., & Gomina, H. E. (2023). Utilisation of electronic resources in the University of Abuja library by undergraduate students. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, 7597. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/7597>.
- Norch, C. K. (2022). Assessing the usage of library electronic resources by postgraduate students at the University of Ghana, Balme Library. *Open Access Library Journal*, 9, 1–17. doi: 10.4236/oalib.1109187.
- Nwabueze, A. U., & Urhiewhu, L. O. (2020). Availability and use of digital information Resources by undergraduates of universities in Delta and Edo States, Nigeria. *International Journal of Digital Library Services*, 5 (2), 41-50
- Obiano, D. C., & Osuji, C. E. (2022). Perceived constraints to the utilisation of ICT facilities in selected university libraries in Imo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Library and Information Science Studies*, 8(1), 33–38.
- Ogbomo, E. F. & Muokebe, B O. (2024). Impact of Library Skills on Value Orientation Among Students: A Global Perspective. *Journal of Educational Research*, 9 (1), 264-285.
- Okunlola, A. A. (2021). Utilisation of library-based electronic resources and services by postgraduates in Nigerian private universities. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary and Current Educational Research (IJM CER)*, 3(4), 164–171.
- Olaniran, S. O., Duma, M. A. N., & Nzima, D. R. (2017). Assessing the utilisation level of e-Learning resources among ODL-based pre-service teacher trainees. *The Electronic Journal of E-Learning*, 15(5), 385–395.
- Olubiyo, P. O., & Olubiyo, L. M. (2023). Strategies for preservation of electronic information resources in academic libraries in Nigeria. *International Journal of Library and Information Science Studies*, 9(3), 50–62. <https://doi.org/10.37745/ijliss.15/vol9n35062>
- Owan, V. A. (2022). Availability of digital resources and institutional compliance with COVID-19 mitigation measures in a Nigerian university. *Electronic Journal of Medical and Educational Technologies*, 15 (4), 23-35
- Owolabi, S., Idowu, O. A., Okocha, F., & Ogundare, A. O. (2019). Utilization of electronic resources by undergraduate students of the University of Ibadan: A case study of social sciences and education. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(3), 23-39
- Perdana, I. A. (2019). Digital library practices in university: Advantages, challenges, and its position. International Conference on Educational Research and Innovation (ICERI 2019).
- Platino, E. C. (2023). Students' assessment and extent of utilization of digital library services in the new normal and its implications for students' academic application. The Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Future of Education, 6(1), 12-25
- Sasikala, C., & Ramahrishna, K. (2017). Use of electronic resources by pharmacy students of GITAM Institute of Pharmacy, GITAM University, Andhra Pradesh, India. *Pearl: A Journal of Library and Information Science*, 11(4), 382-390
- Tekale, R. B., & Dalve, D. B. (2020). E-resources. Review of Research, 1(4), 1–4. <http://www.reviewofresearch.net/PublishArticles/45.aspx>
- Temboqe, A., & Ibraheem, L. D. (2022). Availability and Accessibility of Electronic Information Resources in Federal College of Education Libraries in Northern Nigeria. <https://doi.org/10.5897/ijlis2022.1023>.

- Ternenge, T. S., & Kashimana, F. (2019). Availability, accessibility, and use of electronic information resources for research by students in Francis Sulemanu Idachaba Library, University of Agriculture, Makurdi. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, University of Nebraska–Lincoln.
- Tlakula, T. P., & Fombad, M. (2017). The use of electronic resources by undergraduate students at the University of Venda, South Africa. *The Electronic Library*, 35(5), 861–881.
- Trivedi, M. (2019). Digital Libraries: Functionality, Usability, and Accessibility *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 381.
- Ullah, A., & Usman, M. (2023). Role of libraries in ensuring quality education at higher education institutions: A perspective of Pakistan. *Inverge Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(4), 13–22.
- Urhiewhu, L. O., Okeke, I. E., & Nwafor, M. C. (2015). Extent of digital information resources usage by undergraduates of selected higher institutions in Delta and Edo States, Nigeria. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 5(1), 80-88